

Graphical Visualization of STACK Response Analysis

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Abstract: STACK⁴ offers question types that enable open questions and differentiated feedback based on a response tree. A simple and clear way of analyzing the answers given would make it easier for lecturers to get information about the level of students' knowledge. It would help to discover students' misconceptions and offers the possibility to expand the response tree. In this article we would like to present our work on a graphical interactive visualization of the STACK Response Analysis.

Keywords: STACK, response tree analysis, feedback tree, graphical visualization.

1 Introduction and Objectives

The strengths of digitally supported teaching and learning (electronic learning or e-learning) are the diverse possibilities of interactivity, intelligent evaluation and individual processing of the learning materials independent of time and place. The use of digital learning materials by students is strengthened by integration into a teaching/learning concept and face-to-face teaching. Zeitler [Ze16] introduced the term I-learning, which is taken up in [La19] and described as an interactive, individual, intelligent, integrated e-learning.

The question type STACK, which can be integrated as a plug-in into the learning management systems (LMS) Moodle⁵ and Ilias⁶, offers a perfect basis for building and supporting I-learning with its diverse task possibilities. STACK enables interactive tasks with immediate individual feedback and supports students in their individual learning process (see [Sa13]).

A characteristic core element of STACK questions is the answer tree, on which basis the

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⁴ STACK (System for Teaching and Assessment using a Computer algebra Kernel)
<http://www.stack.ed.ac.uk/>.

⁵ Moodle - Learning Management System <https://moodle.org/>.

⁶ Ilias - Learning Management System <https://www.ilias.de/>.

answer is evaluated and a differentiated individual feedback is given to the learner. The tree is set up in a way, that known errors or misconceptions of the students can be recognized. The learning process is supported with appropriate feedback, suggestions for solutions and sample solutions. (see [St21]). The quality of the feedback depends very much on a very well set up feedback tree. It is therefore very important to have a good understanding of the possible misconceptions for a task.

With the help of an analysis of the implemented answer tree, both the quality of the tree and the students' knowledge of this question can be examined. In particular, an analysis of the answers can provide assistance for the following questions:

- What are the students' learning outcomes? What is their level of knowledge?
- Is the way the feedback tree works, correct? Are the nodes set correctly or are there redundant nodes?
- Can the tree be refined or extended as some answers do not receive differentiated feedback?
- Are there any misconceptions not previously considered in this task?
- Are the variants created, equivalent or are there variants that are significantly more difficult?

The response tree analysis in STACK currently provides a text-based analysis of the given answers. In this paper we present a graphical visualization of the responses according to the structure of the response tree. The goals of the graphical visualization are

- a simple clear presentation of the answers with a good overview of the results,
- an interactive navigation,
- a visualization of response clusters and frequencies,
- a basis for testing the systematic nature of the task and checking the relevance of nodes.

2 Concept and Implementation

In the graphical visualization of the answer tree analysis, a tree with nodes, branches and leaves is built according to the answer tree in the question. The answers that go through a node or end in a leaf are summed up. These values are displayed at the nodes or at the leaves as a total number, as a percentage and as a fill level or progress bar in relation to the total number of answers to this question. The result is a clear representation that can serve as a basis for an analysis of the task or the answers. Some examples of analysis:

- The lecturer has the opportunity to identify which questions the students still have problems with.

- Misconceptions can be identified because there is an unusual accumulation of answers on one leaf.
- Branches in the tree become visible where no answers can be found.
- Variants are discovered that are more difficult than other variants.

The following Fig. 1 illustrates this concept using a very simple example with 100 answers. The responses are checked for properties at each node and the true - false division is visualized at the node using a fill level and a percentage value. For example, the top node shows that 50% have a correct solution and 50% have an incorrect solution. At the next node, the signs of the incorrect answers are checked, which are correct with 20 answers and incorrect with 30 answers. At the end of the answer tree, the analysis shows a cluster of answers on two leaves, indicating a possible refinement of the answer tree.

Fig.1: Concept of graphical visualization of a response tree analysis – example

The core elements of the graphical implementation are summarised below:

1. The answer data is collected from the Moodle database and summed up at each node and for each variant.
2. For each answer, the path through the answer tree is traced. The answers that pass through a node or end in a leaf are summed up and assigned according to the variant used. A graphical interactive visualization is created with the collected data.
3. The graphical visualization of the data is done at the nodes, the branches and the leaves of the answer tree both as a numerical value and as a percentage value, as a

- fill level or progress bar in relation to the total number of answers of this task or a variant.
- 4. It can be chosen whether the graphical visualization should be done for all answers of a task or for each variant separately.
- 5. The tool can be operated interactively, for example, we can navigate between existing task variants and expand and collapse additional information at a node. At a node the individual answers are displayed aggregated and sorted by frequency.
- 6. In addition, it is possible to export the data as a csv file for further use.

3 Examples of graphical visualization

In this section, the different opportunities of graphical visualization of the response tree analysis are presented using a concrete example.

In Fig. 2 an example of a task from the preliminary course in mathematics and the implemented feedback tree with 9 nodes is shown. The task comprises 5 variants and has been answered 3469 times.

Fig.2: Task from a preliminary course in mathematics and its feedback tree

The graphic visualization of the answers to this question follows the same structure as the feedback tree. Fig. 3 shows the overview of the graphic visualization as well as a detailed representation of the branching at node 1. In the branching it can be seen that 52.2% of

users gave a correct answer that corresponds to the sample solution. 47.8% of users gave an answer that contained an error. In the tree following node 2, this error is further narrowed down by further queries.

Fig.3: Graphical visualization of response tree analysis – overview and detailed view of branching at node 1

The graphic visualization is interactive. In this way, further information can be displayed at a node (see Fig. 4). On the one hand, these are details of the query implemented in STACK at this node and, on the other hand, all responses that pass through this node. Furthermore, a summary of identical answers can be displayed and the data can be exported as a file for processing by other programs.

Fig.4: Graphical visualization of response tree analysis – detailed view at node 6

If there are several variants of a task, both the cumulative results of all variants and the answers to each individual variant are interesting. With the cumulative results of all variants, the lecturer can clearly view the level of knowledge of the students. The results of the individual variants and a comparison of these are important for the developer of the task in order to recognize whether one of the variants is possibly easier or more difficult to solve.

The navigation between the variants and the variant summary is easy to carry out, so that a good comparison of the equivalence of the variants is possible and further considerations can be made in order to refine or expand the tree or to remove variants if the degrees of difficulty differ. The Fig. 5 shows the comparison of the 5 variants of this example. The evaluation of the percentage distribution at node 1, which asks whether the solution is correct or not, could indicate that variant 4 is a little more difficult to solve than the other variants. In variant 4, the value of the correct answers was 42.64%, in variants 1 to 3 and 5 it was always over 48.70%.

Fig.5: Investigation of variants of the task

4 Summary and Outlook

In this paper we presented an interactive tool with a graphic visualization of a STACK response analysis. We have explained how this can simplify the viewing of the results and how weak points in the task can be discovered and improved. We have presented a basic version for feedback trees that can be extended to any feedback graphs with additional functionalities.

Bibliography

- [La19] Landefeld, K.; Priebe, J.; Eckhoff, M.: I-Learning – individualisiertes Lernen im Übergang von der Schule in die Hochschule. In (Müller, C., ed.): Zeitschrift für Hochschulentwicklung (ZFHE) Jg. 14/ Nr. 3: Flexibles Lernen an Hochschulen gestalten, pp. 257-271, 2019. <https://zfhe.at/index.php/zfhe/article/view/1261>, accessed: 29/05/2021.
- [Sa13] Sangwin, C.: Computer aided assessment of mathematics. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [St21] STACK (System for Teaching and Assessment using a Computer algebra Kernel)

<http://www.stack.ed.ac.uk/>, accessed: 29/05/2021.

- [Ze16] Zeitler, W.: Humboldt Digital: E-Learning oder I-Learning?. In: Die Neue Hochschule - Jahrgang 2016 - Heft 2, pp. 46-47, 2016. https://hlf.de/fileadmin/hlf-global/downloads/dnh/full/2016/DNH_2016-2.pdf, accessed: 29/05/2021.